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Wireless Big Data of Smart 5G

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Executive Summary

With the advent of the 5G era, mobile Internet, Internet of Things, cloud computing and other types of communication and data processing technology led to the explosive growth of data traffic, and wireless communication network has entered the era of big data. Wireless big data (WBD) has long been used by telecom operators for advanced operations, such as customer service improvement, targeted advertising, service quality optimization and better-informed cooperate decision making. More recently, the use of WBD in combination with vertical industry created an array of new value chains, where there are societal benefits for education, manufacturing, healthcare, smart grid, entertainment, autonomous cars, and smart cities.

5G standardization work is in full swing, and commercial deployment is expected in 2020. Technologies for 5G will provide higher bandwidth, lower latency, and wider connectivity than the current-generation 4G technology. “5G and Beyond” will enable bandwidth in excess of hundreds of Megabits per second (Mb/s) with a latency of less than 1 millisecond (ms), as well as provide connectivity to billions of devices. Most importantly, these technologies are expected to enable fundamentally new applications that will transform the way humanity lives, works, and engages with its environment. The network will thus need to evolve towards cloudification and virtualization to support such diversified and more refined Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. This echoes perfectly with CMCC’s “green and soft” concept since 2009.

To accommodate a range of scenarios and service requirements, the 5G network is becoming more agile, and inevitably, more complicated, thus posing great challenges to real-time radio resource management and network maintenance and optimization. On one aspect, the network needs to intelligently adapt to the environment (e.g., traffic load and user behavior) and the changing service requirements. On another aspect, network automation is desired to replace manual changes according to prior experiences, especially for the ever-increasingly complicated configurations. This paradox calls for the “smart 5G”. 5G network needs to embrace new and cutting-edge technologies such as WBD and artificial intelligence (AI) to efficiently boost both spectrum efficiency and energy efficiency, improve the user experience and reduce the cost.

The members of all stakeholders in industry, academia and standard development organizations recognize the disruptive nature of technologies enabling the WBD enabled “smart 5G” vision, as well as the substantial technical barriers to its realization. Consequently, there is a strong need for developing a technical community to foster the exchange of ideas, sharing of research, the setting of standards, and identification, development, and maturation of system drivers, system specifications, use cases, and supported applications. Once released, this whitepaper will be periodically updated as new research and technologies emerge.

This white paper introduces the concept characteristics and key technologies of WBD and summarizes the values, opportunities and design challenges that the introduction of WBD technologies will bring to the 5G ecosystem. We then outlined the current application areas and envisioned use cases of WBD. We also highlight the WBD enabled network architecture and the requirements for developing host platform and environment. Finally, we describe the potential impact of the introduction of WBD on the 3GPP standards.

Collectively, we think that, with wide range of participation, the knowledge presented here can reduce some of the technical and engineering risks and promote the healthy development of the WBD driven “smart 5G” ecosystem.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	5
2 Wireless Big Data	6
2.1 Understanding of Wireless Big Data	6
2.1.1 Sources.....	7
2.1.2 Category.....	8
2.1.3 Properties	9
2.2 Processing Technology for Wireless Big Data	10
2.2.1 Data Collection	11
2.2.2 Data-based Recognition	11
2.2.3 Decision-making	11
2.3 Potential values of Wireless Big data	11
2.3.1 The Value of Big Data for Operators.....	11
2.3.2 Value of Wireless Big Data for Terminal Users	12
2.3.3 Value of Wireless Big Data for Third-Party Applications.....	12
2.3.4 Value of Wireless Big Data for Wireless Communication Research.....	12
3 Typical Scenarios & Use Cases for Wireless Big Data	13
3.1 Smart Operation & Services	13
3.1.1 Precision marketing	13
3.1.2 3rd Party Applications	13
3.2 Automatic Network Planning & Operation & Maintenance.....	13
3.2.1 Coverage Hole Discovery	13
3.2.2 QoE issue debugging	14
3.2.3 Network Energy Efficiency Optimization	15
3.2.4 Multi-Access Edge Computing Deployment	17
3.3 Intelligent Network Design & Optimization.....	18

3.3.1	Network Slicing Optimization	18
3.3.2	Service type Recognition for Traffic	18
3.3.3	Customized Mobility Management.....	19
3.3.4	Context Aware Cross-Layer Optimization	20
3.3.5	Proactive Network Resource Management.....	20
3.3.6	Coverage and Capacity Optimization	23
3.3.7	Virtual Grid Enabled Network Performance Optimization	24
3.3.8	User Portraits Enabled User Experience Optimization	25
3.4	Emerging Physical Layer Technology.....	26
3.4.1	Wireless Big Data Assisted Channel Modeling.....	26
3.4.2	Wireless Big Data Enabled Spectrum Map.....	27
3.4.3	Agile PHY Transmission Optimization	29
4	Wireless Big Data Enabled Network Architecture.....	31
4.1	Architecture	31
4.2	Big Data Module Function Definition	33
4.3	Interface	33
5	Wireless Big Data Platform Capabilities/Environment.....	34
5.1	Platform Requirements and Definitions.....	34
5.2	Framework of wireless big data platform	35
5.3	Data representation in wireless big data platform.....	36
6	Impact on the Standardization	37
6.1	Standards progress in 3GPP SA2.....	37
6.2	Potential Impact on 3GPP RAN3	38
7	Summary.....	38
	Reference.....	39
	Glossary.....	40
	Acknowledgement.....	42

1 Introduction

Nowadays, the importance of big data (BD) is recognized by almost all industries, where data can be used to drive industrial development and digital innovations stem from data become essential. Governments of many countries have paid great attention to big data. The United States released The Federal Big Data Research and Development Strategic Plan, and invested 200 million dollars for the development of big data in order to improve homeland security, to change the educational learning pattern, to accelerate innovation in science and engineering. Internet companies are at the forefront of such technologies, such as Google, Facebook Baidu, and Alibabaa. Each company has launched its own series of BD-labeled products and system designs. The telecom companies joined the party at a later date, but they have an unparalleled advantage of data resources. The large amount of phones and the wide communication network coverage provide various data resources. Among the 120+ telecom operators, 48% of them already started to implement big-data-aided strategic plans and made fruitful achievements. Verizon in the United States has established a big data research lab specifically for exploring new use case ideas and foster real-life products and services. Meanwhile, a precision marketing department was also set up to carry out analysis on consumer needs and to provide business consulting services for other companies, all based on their extensive database.

Apart from big data, artificial intelligent (AI) can't be ignored. In 2015, the number of AI related enterprises in the world reached 806, and it is estimated that every 10.9 hours a new AI company is born on average. Over the past year, nearly 10 billion US dollars is invested in the field of AI. AI has been heeded by the Chinese government, and the term is written into "the national 13th Five-Year Plan" as a key research and industrialization focus. Big companies across the world are increasing their investments in the field. For instance, Google and Baidu have launched their AI strategic plan, aiming at applying AI to people's daily lives. Telecom operators also join the exploration and use this new technology for applications such as voice recognition and deep learning for new product and service development. NTT DOCOMO in Japan proposed "Smart Life" strategy combining BD and AI as an integrated service. China mobile, as the world's largest mobile operator, is one of early implementer of BD analytics to support its operational, management and business actions, as well as to create innovative applications.

In the era of 5G and beyond, a plethora of use cases and their distinctive communication requirements are emerging. The mobile network needs to be responsive and adapts with various parameters and processes (e.g. frame structure, duplex mode, and transport layer protocols) across the network, since each use case entails complex propagation environments, constantly changing user profiles and service profiles. Real-time or near-real-time RRM becomes challenging as resource allocation on the frequency/time/code/spatial domains are not optimal and sometimes wasteful. Meanwhile, the management and optimization of 5G network also faces unprecedented challenges with the diversified of deployment scenarios and service requirements. The automatic network control method based on a closed-loop scheme is desired to replace the traditional manual methods. This paradox calls for the "smart 5G".

Wireless BD (WBD) and AI are widely recognized as the two main driving forces for “smart 5G”. Driven by a large amount of authentic network data, together with communication theory, data mining, statistical analysis, deep learning, and many other AI technologies, the network performance, efficiency and user experience are envired to be significantly enhanced with much reduced network costs.

Before diving into more detailed description of the possible use cases and applications, in the next section, we will firstly begin with the consensus on some important basic issues with WBD, such as sources, definition and characteristics. Then, we describe the processes and technologies associated with the current WBD applications. Finally, a round-up of foreseeable values that wireless big data can add to the whole communication system, e.g., applications and services, network, and transmission, will be presented.

2 Wireless Big Data

2.1 Understanding of Wireless Big Data

The McKinsey Global Institute has published the following definition for big data: “the scale of data exceeds the capability of acquisition, storage, management and analysis for conventional data-base software, which can be characterized by the massive amount of data, fast data flow, diversified data type, and low data value density.” Big data has firstly been incorporated with computer science, with applications including massive parallel processing, data base, data mining, distributed file system, cloud computation platform, Internet, and scalable storage system. Big data is inseparable with cloud computing, where big data processing adopts distributed computing architecture to achieve the distributed data mining for massive amount of data.

Due to the broadening of spectrum, the increasing of user and the base station density, and the diversification of services, such as the rapid development of IoT and IoV, the future wireless communication exhibits notable characteristics of big data, along with various characteristics of mobile communication. The massive amount of data generated from the wireless communication services, as well as the massive amount of data from the transmission, access, network, and application, are named wireless big data, as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure. 2.1 Concept of Wireless Big Data

2.1.1 Sources

The source of big data can be mainly classified into three categories, raw data, processed and derived data, and experiment Data.

- Raw Data

The data can originate from the wireless and mobile services of massive number of users, including the occupation of wireless spectrum, the access method of wireless air interface, the wireless network traffic, and wireless application profile. Such data can be characterized directly by the wireless communication behavior, and acquired from the measurement meters, the user terminals, the base station/core network equipments, and application services, before being organized into data sets. The data sets can be categorized as the following, the physical-layer big data (e.g., channel big data), the media-access layer big data (e.g., the wireless access behavior), the network-layer big data (e.g., the network flow data), and the application-layer big data (e.g., the service requirements of users).

- Processed and Derived Data

Such type of big data refers to the data, model, distribution, statistics, and trends generated from the processing of original raw wireless big data, e.g., the distribution of spectrum availability, the spatial distribution of ultra-dense cells, the resource allocation for transmission. The processing includes real-time processing and offline processing. The data from real-time processing can be applied to the real-time user access and transmission mode selection. The data from offline processing can be applied to the long-term user access and service behavior statistics, for the

perspectives of cell and spectrum planning.

- Experimental Data

Such big data refers to the data set generated from lab tests, field trials, pre-commercial network trials, and the commercial network test, as all for the evaluation of unexplored spectrum, novel transmission techniques, novel access and revolutionary network architecture. Due to the differences in volume and characteristics of such data set as compared to the previous two types, it is challenging to come up with fair and effective comparative analysis method.

2.1.2 Category

Wireless big data can be classified into transmission-layer big data, network-layer big data, and application-layer big data as shown in Table. 2.1. The three types of big data can be illustrated as follows

- **Transmission-layer Big Data**

Such type of big data refers to the channel big data, the spectrum big data and multi-user access big data. Concrete examples include the link quality at different positions, across the spectrum, and for a massive number of users. Take wireless channel modeling as an example, one can make use big data analytics to help achieve a balance between the accuracy and the complexity requirements. There are state-of-the-art modeling method based on Principal component analysis (PCA) that can extract wireless propagation features. As for spectrum big data, one can use it to construct networks that rely on big data analysis for dynamic spectrum access to maximize spectrum utilization rate. Finally, the wireless sensor network modeling in cognitive radio can be modeled as the statistics problem of distributed spectrum access in unknown environments through studying the big data from multi-user access information, so as to improve the performance of access points.

- **Network-layer Big Data**

Network-layer big data includes the cell configuration parameters, for example the radio-frequency antenna configuration data, the uplink and downlink configuration data, the network interference data, the network load data, and the signaling data. Such types of data can be applied to the network flow analysis and network optimization. Wireless traffic flow monitoring and analysis system can well support the emerging area of big data analysis. The mobile user behavior can be investigated from three perspectives, the data usage, mobile pattern, and application usage. Based on the resource consumption in the mobile Internet, it can be concluded that the heavy flow users and highly mobile users tend to consume large amount of data and wireless resources. The network planning and resource allocation can be improved and optimized based on the big data analysis. Communication network optimization can be conducted based on the feature of data collected from the user equipments. Breakthroughs in those works are still needed in both theoretical and practical perspectives.

- **Application-layer Big Data**

Application-layer big data is varied, including the user mobile data, the social network data, the IoT data, the daily life data, the unmanned aircraft generated data. The user mobile data is crucial to the resource

allocation, network planning, content distribution, and handover for wireless communication, where the current works mainly focus on the mobility pattern extraction/analysis/prediction, the analysis of WiFi/GPS trace record and network traffic flow. It is a challenge to obtain the individual behavior from massive social network data. Such problem can be solved via establishing a neighborhood adjacent framework, the user clustering based on the matrix singular value decomposition (SVD), and neighborhood behavior prediction based on the individual behavior analysis. The massive sensor in the IoT can collect the massive data in the real space, which can describe human behavior in a real-time manner. Unmanned aircraft and automobile can collect and store the various application data in urban areas.

Table 2.1 Three Categories of Wireless Big Data

Data Category	Contents
<u>Application-layer Big Data</u>	Content popularity, service type, user preference, location, mobility, user behavior, etc
<u>Network-layer Big Data</u>	Cell configurations, downlink and uplink signal strength, traffic load, outage rate, inter/intra-cell interference, signaling, UE capability, etc.
<u>Transmission-layer Big Data</u>	Physical channel information such as path loss, shadowing, channel statistics, etc.

2.1.3 Properties

The main characteristics of WBD include the following aspects.

- Big Volume**
 Wireless big data can be featured by its huge volume and fast generation speed. An example in the transmission-layer data, where huge amount of data can be generated from the physical-layer channel data and the computing process. It is reported that in the China Mobile Network, the amount of DPI generated data increases several hundreds of TBs per day.
- Huge Dimension**
 The data can be featured from diversified origin and classification. The user behavior can be analyzed via multi-dimensional data, such as the joint analysis from the network data and application data.
- High Quality**
 The user data can be featured by high reliability, for example the real-name data which is typically associated with a unique mobile number. The user data can be accurately associated with the network data.
- Timeliness**
 There are certain near real-time requirements on the collection and mining of wireless big data. The

collection of near real-time wireless big data refers to the fast acquisition of transmission related big data, e.g., the channel state information, network flow, and user data, and sending them to the analysis and mining entity for further processing. This is one of the most challenging aspect, yet highly demanded by the next-generation WBD applications. One of the difficulties lie in the design at the user terminal, where less complex computing and less reporting are desirable, while it is much simpler at the server side to have parallel computing capability to handle complex analysis tasks and produce accurate results.

- **Complicated Association**

To better utilize the wireless big data, it is necessary to build association among the data from the application layer, the network layer, and the transmission layer. The association among the wireless big data is typically complicated, where the data from different layers may have different time scales and traits. For example, a user is identified by C-RNTI in radio access network, and by IMEI in the core network. So in applications, different IMEI, AndroidID, Cookie, UA and cell phone numbers should be associated and accurately matched.

2.2 Processing Technology for Wireless Big Data

Figure 2.2 Big Data Processing

2.2.1 Data Collection

Current data collection are mainly performed by telecommunication operators, telecommunication equipments manufacturers and application service providers, and will be possibly extended to other collection systems, such as Internet of Things, industry systems. Collection nodes include smart phones, laptop and many other sensor nodes in the terminal side, macro/micron base stations or access points in cellular networks and IoT systems at access network side and data collection units at the core network side. Collection techniques include raw data recording and DPI (deep packet inspection).

2.2.2 Data-based Recognition

Data recognition means recognizing the inherent categories, statistical disciplines, data trends and spatio-temporal patterns in the massive data set through classification, clustering, estimation, prediction and visualization. The primary aim of recognition is to analyze and mine the hidden normal and abnormal events and the correlations between them. Leveraging the visualization tools, data scientists can obtain the problems, errors, anomalies in the wireless communication systems.

2.2.3 Decision-making

Big data decision making process includes statistical inference, hypothesis test and optimizations, where inference seeks and confirms the reason of problems, tests verify the conclusions from the recognition, and optimization will continuously improve the target systems. By the technologies mentioned above, the decision and plans can be applied to the system in a iterative manner.

2.3 Potential values of Wireless Big data

2.3.1 The Value of Big Data for Operators

Wireless big data is the core resource for operators ' intelligence operation, which can effectively support intelligent management and external data service. By promoting the whole network data collection, aggregation and effective association, building enterprise-level big data platforms, forming enterprise-level open Data Environment, operators can provide data services for different customers including service providers.

By analysing and mining user data and application data, operator can have complete user profile and subsequent behavioural prediction, such as service needs and preferences. Such information are useful in improving products, formulating marketing strategies and providing value-adding services, e.g. precision marketing, customized services, improving marketing success rate and overall service quality. By means of data mining and coverage diagram analysis, we can understand whether a certain region needs to increase its network coverage to enhance the user experience, in the forms

of carrying out network optimization or new base station deployments. It is beneficial to integrate internal and external data, share data analytical tools, promote data cross correlation modelling, and mining. Increasing active cooperation with diversified vertical industries can eliminate any data island, and create an ecosystem that thrives with sharing progresses and results, and ultimately contribute to the societal developments in both private and public sectors.

2.3.2 Value of Wireless Big Data for Terminal Users

The important value of wireless big data to end users is embodied in two aspects. First, end users can gain a better wireless service experience by sharing data. In the future, with the popularization of relevant applications and the maturity of laws and regulations, end users can further obtain economic returns by sharing data. Secondly, with the continuous improvement of terminal hardware performance, end users can actively participate in the wireless large-data industry chain, such as sharing terminal processing capabilities, preprocessing raw data, developing data-driven innovative applications, etc.

2.3.3 Value of Wireless Big Data for Third-Party Applications

The most obvious values of wireless big data for third-party applications are clients profile characterization, clients credit estimation, cooperate decision making and investment strategy in innovative R&D, all of which can promote better management, operation efficiency, and the service quality. The third-party application can further cooperate with the wireless big data industrial chain, by integrating internal data and external data and promoting the cross-association and data mining analysis. Such cooperation can help to break free of the data island and further investigate the innovative applications and business models for next-level development.

2.3.4 Value of Wireless Big Data for Wireless Communication Research

Last but not least, investigating WBD is going to be most rewarding from the wireless communication research standpoint. Here are some clear beneficial cases: the information bits can be mined and inferred by establishing deep learning networks, and new codes can be designed to further approach channel capacity; huge amount of data from a ultra wideband can be reduced according to the dimensionality reduction principle, and further used to get the correlation to channel capacity, which can guide optimal transmission across a wide spectrum, such as at the millimeter wave and optical wave band; big data can also be used in the transmission mode selection, especially for multi-node networks, by using reinforcement learning based decision model, which can predict the optimal transmission mode under certain channel condition and user application requirements.

With the development of the intelligent network in the future, data analytics can be used to sense and predict the user's service requirement and mobility pattern, so as to achieve the customized mobility management, the precise allocation of resources and the optimization of the energy consumption of the network. Wireless big data analysis may also predict the trend of wireless network development.

3 Typical Scenarios & Use Cases for Wireless Big Data

3.1 Smart Operation & Services

3.1.1 Precision marketing

Traditional recommendation in telecom industry is generally the same for all the users, and the individual need is usually not considered. This can be significantly optimized by analyzing the user behavior data. Through big data analytics, we may excavate the true needs of the individual users and find their key interests. The users can be classified into sub-groups based on their behaviors through clustering algorithm, second clustering algorithm, decision tree algorithm and so on. The sub-group can be matched with relevant customized marketing strategy. Bundled recommendation and sales, more attractive promotional projects can be carried out improve marketing success rate.

3.1.2 3rd Party Applications

There is no doubt that operators' big data will bring great benefits for the public services. The real-time user location information extracted from the real-time base station signaling data can be utilized for analyzing the city's overall flow of people. It provides important support for public safety. By monitoring the flow of people in real time, especially, the large-scale spatial location movement, it helps to find out the potential safety risk. The base station signaling data can also record the moving trajectories of the users. By using the user mobile sequence detection technology and key location mining algorithm along with the matching algorithm between mobile device spatial-temporal trajectories and real-time road network, we can compute and show the real time urban traffic and provide valuable suggestions for urban road construction.

3.2 Automatic Network Planning & Operation & Maintenance

3.2.1 Coverage Hole Discovery

Network KPIs can be clarified into Accessibility, Retainability, Availability, Mobility, Traffic and Radio Quality. Operators use KPI (Key Performance Indicator) to monitor how well network is performing. Bad radio coverage can impact network KPI significantly. If coverage hole could be efficiently recognized and optimized, it will improve KPI. It's time and man power costly to find coverage hole with drive testing. On wireless big data platform, it makes coverage hole recognition easily and efficiently. It's done via statistics (clustering) based on information collected in wireless big data platform, such as call trace, UE measurement report, base station

measurement result, location and other input.

From network point of view, it's not easy to locate UE position precisely without positioning feature enabled. It's a fact that most of network doesn't enable positioning feature. Generally, triangulation is the way used to estimate UE location. It uses base station position (preconfigured by operator) and direction together with UE reported RSRP/RSRQ to do the calculation. It will work but the precision couldn't be guaranteed. using 'novel machine learning algorithms by combining elements from supervised learning based RF finger-printing and particle-filter based Hidden Markov Model learning used for robot path-tracking'[1] can achieve median accuracy of 20 – 30 m. It has significant improvement comparing to no machine learning which is about 100 m. With this more accurate positioning info, together with call drop event, handover failure event and RRC re-establishment event, it can quickly identify area of weak coverage or coverage hole. Exhibiting the result in the map, it will guide maintenance team to perform optimization.

In the following figure (Verizon field), red colored dot exhibits coverage hole calculated based on UE location, UE reported RSRP and call drop/handover failure event.

Figure 3.1 coverage hole exhibition based on location

3.2.2 QoE issue debugging

Good KPI could be an indicator that network element work at its best, but it cannot assure to meet the end user expectation. Modern operators shift to QoE (Quality of Experience) monitoring and optimization which target to improve the end user satisfaction. QoE is more of subjective experience. Many factors such as personal mood could impact the user perception. From network point of view, in order shift to QoE optimization, some KQI (Key Quality Indicator) are defined. KQI could be MOS for voice, webpage downloading time, Round Trip Time, delay, jitter, packet loss rate etc.

In the wireless big data platform, there're collections of traces from radio access network, core network, including control plane signaling, user plane data and a variety of real-time measurement data. For a given user, it's

possible to correlate information from different network elements. For example, using time stamp, the unique identity of the interface in the network element, it can form an overview of a user. With all such history data and using machine learning algorithm, the performance problem of a given user could be automatically identified by the system e.g: using decision tree, and the results are clustered and classified by big data analysis.

When a user is surfing the internet, if requested webpage could be returned within 1 s, the user feels good. If the page returns more than 5s, the experience would be awful. On wireless big data platform, it can recognize all users experiencing webpage downloading rates below a given threshold, e.g: 64 kbps for DL or 32 kbps for UL. All such users can be categorized to identify network coverage problems, device problems, terminal problems, or application server problems through decision trees machine learning algorithm. All the possible bad behaved user records are summarized and clarified; maintenance and development engineer can take this input for further checking and optimization.

Figure 3.2 Decision tree used for low user throughput classification

3.2.3 Network Energy Efficiency Optimization

◇ Dynamic enable/disable secondary carrier

KPI data of network data volume, radio resource utilization with time of day statistics reveal that there's daytime busy hours and nighttime idle hours. It's consistent with the human's work and rest rhythm. With more and more 4G network users and intelligent terminal applications appears, the idle time of night start postponed. There is also a significant tidal effect between office buildings and residential areas. In order to improve the network coverage and user experience, operators deploy multiple carrier frequencies for hot spot. LTE advance features such as carrier aggregation can improve throughput significantly.

Power saving is one of OPEX for operators. On the wireless big data platform, various cycles can be achieved by the analysis of history data of resource utilization, traffic volumes. As there're also detail application traffic information, more application behavior can be classified with periodicity and trends. With the location information,

it can identify different types of coverage area for clustering. Based on the current collection of network resource usage and periodicity of change, it can provide guidance of switching ON/OFF the secondary carrier frequency. Compared to the base station method which is based on real-time resource utilization, the number of online users to manage the extra carrier switch ON/OFF, big data platform can be more accurately predict the demand for resources, reduce the unnecessary ping-pong effect.

The following figure shows the network traffic volume usage with hour of day. Time period between 23:00 and 6:00 are not shown. Secondary carrier could be dynamically switched ON/OFF based on the real network resource usage.

Figure 3.3 hourly network traffic volume

◇ Multi-RAT Cooperation Energy-Saving

To cope with the severe energy challenges caused by incessant mobile network expansion, the multi-RAT cooperation energy-saving system (MCES) was developed to effectively improve the energy efficiency of mobile networks. MCES interacts with the radio access network in a real-time manner and can support multiple vendors' 2G/3G/4G RAN equipment. MCES identifies and coordinates cells with overlapping coverage to achieve network energy-savings. Through big data analytics of massive MR data and traffic profiles, MCES can find the energy-saving cells and their compensating cell, and predict their traffic load trends. When the traffic load meets the criteria, for example, falling below some pre-defined threshold for some time, MCES will migrate its traffic to the compensating cell and place the energy-saving cell into a sleep state. With a real-time monitoring function, MCES can also turn on the sleeping cell before high-volume traffic arrives abruptly.

Up to now, MCES has been deployed for over 70000 cells across 10 provinces in China. The average annual electricity saving is 400000 kwh in 10000 cell area.

Figure 3.4 Illustrations of MCES

3.2.4 Multi-Access Edge Computing Deployment

The Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) is one of key technology enablers for 5G and its application. The major functionality of MEC is to move service logic within the Cloud-in-the-Center to the network edge, and let the logic as much closer to users as possible. In order to meet the challenges from 5G scenario e.g. enhanced mobile band, massive connectivity and huge data volume, ultra low latency and high reliability, the IT service, environments and computing capability for 5G application need be wildly distributed to reasonable locations and closed to user and base station.

Once obtained accurate user profile by analyzing collected big data, the deployment requirements for MEC targeted for each vertical could become clear. In the network edge which closed to user, it is easier to perform user data collection in real time, and collected data is firsthand and real. Those data are from multiple dimensions: including but not limited to data related to locations, times, terminals, user behaviors and etc. After analyze those real-name data, accurate user profile including their interesting, social relations, patterns regarding every daily activities and etc can be obtained. With those accurate profiles, personalized MEC deployment could be achieved in flexible, efficient and customized way. For example, based on result of big data analyze, Over-The-Top operators could deploy video service MEC server targeted to specific areas, and commercial service provider could launch marketing campaigns for targeted customers at specific network edge.

Take Vehicular Networking (V2X) application as an example, by analyzing big data gathered from road, vehicles and human behaviors, and locating V2X server close to above data source, then creative V2X services which with low latency and high reliable characteristics could be provided in more convenient way. The V2X MEC server could provide following information to vehicles/drivers: reminder for brake, alert for anti-possible-collision for crossroad, reminders for roadside constructions, pedestrian and breakdown vehicles, and reminder for safety driving, as well as provide the optimal route planned for high priority vehicles such as ambulances. By analyzing

those collected big data and sharing the result, assisted automatic driving could be achieved without involving expensive radars which has the limitation that full coverage/journey sensing is not achievable. Additionally, by analyzing real-time collected data at network edge e.g. data from radar and video surveillance, more and more V2X application could be developed.

3.3 Intelligent Network Design & Optimization

3.3.1 Network Slicing Optimization

Next generation (5G) wireless network shall support services of different characteristic. It supports Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC), massive Machine Type Communications(mMTC) in addition to what has been supported in LTE network (e.g: mobile broadband, VoLTE). Different service has different requirements over wireless network, e.g: real-time video, voice service is more sensitive to delay but has relative loose requirement over packet loss rate; intelligent meter like IoT devices has strict requirement over reliability but loose requirement over bandwidth and delay. 5G introduces network slice in order to meet the diverse requirements of various services in the same physical network instruments. Network slice is a logical concept by assigning services with the same network requirements to a slice. Different network slices are logically independent of each other and physically share the same network resources.

Per experience of traditional network planning, engineers should build traffic model and then configure resource reservation of each slide. The difficulty here is that there's no such data available and traffic model cannot reflect real resource requirement. On wireless big data platform, there're collection of user traffic data (e.g: via DPI) and location info. With statistic/analysis of packets, it can cluster services based on application behavior and its resource requirements, devices distribution and periodicity. It can predict slice resource requirements by using machine learning and feedback to network element for auto tuning.

3.3.2 Service type Recognition for Traffic

Currently, varieties of service types are flowing through the LTE network, but only the VoLTE (Voice over LTE) service based on dedicated EPS bearer is handled separately. While others services are all aggregated into the default EPS bearer. The LTE network processed the traffic flows based on packet filters, but it cannot aware the service information (e.g. service type, priority) for a traffic flow marked by its packet filter.

However, in the future, more varieties of service types will be introduced into the 5G network, which leads to more and more network or wireless resource shortages, so it is meaningful for the network to recognize the service types of the traffic, for example, to improve the service experience for OTT or vertical industries etc. or to optimize the network operations for the operators.

Traditional approaches (e.g. DPI, Deep Packet Inspection) for service type recognition are based on HTTP packet head or content. But the new HTTPs packet head or content has been enciphered which resulted in these

traditional approaches failure. Therefore, it is needed to explore other approaches like big data based service classification method for service type recognition.

During the big data based service recognition, big data analysis network element could,

- collect data from the 3rd Application platform, the 3GPP network or the UE
- perform service classification model hypothesis and training based on the data
- predict the service type for new packet flows from the network

Based on the service recognition, network could perform differentiation serves with different services.

3.3.3 Customized Mobility Management

5G registration area will be similar to 4G tracking area. The registration area list is maintained in both UE and AMF, and 5G RAN still needs to broadcast registration area code to UE. There may exist three mobility categories for UE e.g. No mobility/Restricted mobility/Unrestricted mobility.

Without big data, it will be very difficult to track and categorize UE's mobility pattern. Therefore it looks beneficial leverage big data analysis to mine the collected network information to precisely predict UE's mobility pattern and the associated UE track e.g. gNB list or cell list per time of day and then feedback the above data analytics to network, allowing AMF to page the UE via e.g. gNB list or cell list and therefore bring down the paging load in gNB and saving corresponding processing resource in gNB.

The handover parameters have close relationship with different network propagation environments (such as building occlusion), interference, load, and service types. If the handover parameters are set unreasonably, premature handover, late handover, or a ping-pong handover maybe occurs, which deteriorates the handover performance and load balancing performance, and finally results in poor user experience. Big data analysis can be used to collect and learn handover data in different network environments, such as different cells, slices, user types, and service types, and then to predict cell interference, load and user service performances, and adaptively to set handover parameter configurations.

In general, traditional methods always make handover decisions based on instantaneous measurements. The big data analysis algorithms could fully exploited to mine the historical information and predictive information during handover procedures which help make intelligent decisions.

Figure 3.5 Customized Mobility Management

3.3.4 Context Aware Cross-Layer Optimization

While the radio condition of the mobile network can fluctuate on the order of milliseconds and may occasionally result in packet losses even without network congestion, the application is adjusted on a larger timescale on the order of seconds and tends to attribute packet loss to network overloading. As a result, there is a misalignment between the radio access network (RAN) and the application, which may lead to non-effective usage of available radio resources and a degraded user experience. Therefore, it is highly desirable to introduce cross-layer optimization between the RAN and the application. RAN may inform the application of the real-time radio air-interface channel status, based on which the application adjusts its transmission data rate. Take TCP optimization for example, with some useful RAN information, e.g., buffer size, load of the base station (BS), the link throughput, and service type, packet error rate (PER), the TCP congestion window can be optimized and predicted to better match the radio channel variations. However, it is extremely hard to find a mathematical cross-layer model to determine the optimal TCP window with so many affecting factors. In this case, big data assisted machine learning based optimization offers an effective solution. With well constructed training data, a supervised learning based model can be trained for the TCP window prediction. The big data assisted learning approach allows for a good match between the TCP window and the wireless channel condition. This will significantly improve system throughput and buffer utilization.

RAN may also identify the traffic features or traffic priorities within the application sessions via the big data analytics. Accordingly, the RAN can dynamically reconfigure its network protocols and parameters and performs prioritized scheduling strategies to guarantee traffic transmission of higher priority.

3.3.5 Proactive Network Resource Management

Recent big data analysis has revealed the possibility of predicting human behavior [2]. Based on the regularity of human activities and habits, it is possible to predict the space-time distribution of traffic load, understand the probabilities of contents that users may request, and predict where and when the network will be congested. Based on user mobility and traffic pattern prediction, wireless resource management methods can be optimized in a

predictive manner. Specifically, on one hand, content can be proactively cached. On the other hand, traffic loads can be balanced in a larger time-space scale by predictive resource allocation and intelligent association, which dramatically improves the efficiency of resource utilization. In the following, we discuss the wireless resource management schemes enabled by wireless big data analysis from three aspects: proactive caching, predictive radio resource allocation and intelligent association of user equipment.

✧ **Proactive Caching**

Proactive caching predicts the contents that users may request and cache them at nodes of the wireless edge, e.g., base station (BS) and user equipment, before users send the requests. The major approaches of proactive caching are caching at BSs, cache-enabled D2D communications, and pushing. When users send requests, the requested contents can be found from the cache of nearby nodes (e.g., macro BSs, pico BSs, or even user equipment) immediately and then were sent to the users, which can improve user experience [3], reduce end-to-end delay, and boost overall network performance efficiently [4-7].

To implement proactive caching, we need to resort to big data analysis to predict the contents to be proactively cached. In traditional wired networks, contents are stored at the content server, usually in a reactive manner. Since the content server has large storage size and covers a large number of users in a large time-space range, it is possible to predict the content popularity by big data analysis. However, in wireless networks, due to the limited size of storage and coverage area of BSs, designing caching policies based on the content popularity cannot improve caching gain efficiently. This is because the content popularity as a demand of multiple users cannot reflect the demand of each individual user, which results in lower cache-hit ratio and degrades the gain of improving network performance and user satisfactory. Therefore, to improve the gain of proactive caching, we need to predict the probability of each user requesting each file (i.e., user preference) and active level of each user. How to quickly learn user preference and active level for large number of users with low complexity in practical environment with dynamically generated contents is an urgent task to be solved. Due to the limited number of user requests obtained at the base station, the predicted file request probability is not accurate. How to design cache policies under these imperfect factors is also an inevitable problem.

✧ **Predictive Resource Allocation**

Traditional wireless systems are designed for end-to-end communication, which assume that the required contents, the request time, the user location, and the user trajectory are random. In these scenarios, the static resource allocation scheme is considered in wireless radio access. In other word, there is a fixed matching between the association resources (e.g. radio spectrum and base station) and radio access technology (RAT). As a result, the resource allocation scheme cannot be adjusted adaptively according to the dynamic tendency of spectrum and traffic load. In the network that is designed based on such principle, the unbalanced space-time distribution of traffic causes that the BSs in hot spots are overloaded, but there are a lot of idle resources in other BSs or in idle time.

Predictive resource allocation makes the plan for radio resources allocation in advance based on the prediction of the network environment, channel quality, and traffic demand. For example, for real-time traffic (e.g., phone calls

and video conference), it is possible to ensure user experience quality (QoE) by forecasting the traffic demands and reserving resources. For non-real-time traffic (e.g., video on demand (VoD) and file download traffic), it is possible to borrow future residual resources to improve the overall network resource utilization with the individual QoE guarantee, according to the user required content, quality of service (QoS) requirements, and the prediction of user trajectory, channel statistics, and interference statistics. For predictive resource allocation, the related context information includes application level (e.g., QoE of VoD, video conference, voice and other traffic), network level information (e.g., congestion status, spectrum and interference environment), user level information (e.g., mobility trajectory and the average channel gains in corresponding locations), and device level information (available storage capacity and remaining battery capacity of mobile terminals). So far, the existing research on predictive resource allocation considers the user-level or network-level context information to allocate resource in advance, which can improve network throughput [8], reduce transmission costs, enhance user experience [11,12] and lower network congestion [13-15].

Effective predictive resource allocation requires to predict user behavior, network traffic and spectrum situation. The predicted information relies on a mass of comprehensive data about wireless environments, users, mobile traffic, and so on from low-level layer to high-level layer, which raises a higher demand to the network function than before. On the existing network configuration, it is necessary to deploy the radio spectrum data collection module on the edge network (such as the BS), introduce the network traffic acquisition and recognition module at the convergence layer (e.g. the gateway), and add the matching module between the traffic information and the traffic data in the core network. Moreover, since the high dynamic characteristic of the wireless environment causes the stringent requirements on data collection, feedback and processing cycles, it is necessary to introduce high-rate, high-reliability and low-latency control information exchanging channels in existing network systems. In addition, the massive data generated by the dense data collection module causes serious challenges on the control network, hence it is also necessary to solve the problem of all kinds of data collectors deployment.

✧ **Intelligent Network Access Control**

The existing strategies of wireless device access to different-mode networks and different access points (AP) rely on a single instantaneous indicator, such as the received signal strength and the theoretical rate. The limitations of traditional access strategies in the future network have become increasingly obvious. For example, in a millimeter-wave communication network, due to the small coverage of the network, the traditional access strategies lead to frequent switching among different APs (i.e., ping-pong effect), where redundant switching severely degrades the user's throughput. In addition, for Internet of Things applications, the diverse service-quality requirements and the special device characteristics make it difficult for massive devices to access the networks quickly and easily [16]. In order to realize the intelligent access of wireless devices, the instantaneous information will no longer be the only basis for decision-making, the historical information and forecasted information will also be taken into account. In particular, the historical data to be utilized include the network information such as received signal values, device status information, device geospatial information, throughput and latency.

Wireless big data contain information closely related to the network behavior and the user behavior, which brings great opportunities for intelligent wireless access. With the help of big data analysis, we can extract the

space-time variability and relevance of wireless service/user/network behaviors, and provide basis for decision-making to realize intelligent and efficient wireless access [17]. There are still many problems to solve for big data enabled wireless access, including the assessment of the service quality of different networks, the establishment of a unified assessment system. Also, how to handle the huge feedback generated by massive devices to assist decision-making is not clear. It is also important to transfer the extracted knowledge from offline analysis of massive historical data to specific real environment for real-time online decision-making.

In order to realize wireless big data enabled intelligent wireless network, the network structure needs to integrate the following modules. First of all, an offline analysis module is required in the cloud to achieve joint mining and complex analysis of big data. The high-level semantic knowledge is extracted through the complex mining of the multi-modal data and will be used for the whole network. Secondly, a semi-real-time analysis module is required in the local base stations (group) to localize the off-line extracted knowledge. The module will combine the high-level semantic knowledge provided by the cloud and the local information to derive knowledge suitable for local learning. Then, an online real-time analysis module is required in edge devices to achieve real-time matching of highly dynamic networks. The module will combine the localized semantic information and real-time measured data to make quick decisions. Finally, to realize the sharing and regeneration of knowledge in the whole network, a separate knowledge flow network is required to add to the existing data transmission network, for continuously improving the intelligence of the whole network.

3.3.6 Coverage and Capacity Optimization

Coverage and capacity optimization (CCO) is one of the typical operational tasks of the radio access network (RAN). CCO aims to provide the required capacity in the targeted coverage areas, to minimize the interference and maintain an acceptable quality of service in an autonomous way. To achieve these targets, antenna power and configuration (pilot power, antenna down tilt, antenna azimuth, or massive MIMO pattern in 5G) play a critical role, as they affect the direction of the antenna radiation pattern. Fixed RF parameters could not bring the best network performance for the ever-changing radio network environment. CCO can be used to improve the received signal strength in the own cell as well as to reduce the interference to neighboring cells by selecting appropriate RF parameters.

The network is very complicated, and it is not possible to find definite function to map between the RF parameters and the target coverage and capacity performance. The main reason is that the set of configurable RF parameters is multi-dimensional, and each RF parameter has wide range of values, leading to very large number of possible options.

Reinforcement learning with neural network is used to adjust RF parameters for COO. The algorithm can leverage machine learning to analyze and learn what the proper action is for each current network state. Neural network is used to build the mapping between network states, RF parameters and the network performance. Compared to the traditional Q-table method, it has better generalization ability and can respond to changes in the wireless network in a good way. The algorithm also punishes KPI violations. This policy guarantees the network KPI remaining stable during the process of CCO.

RF optimization based on CCO can be used in many scenarios, such as carrier aggregation (CA), energy saving, and SFN. CA scenario is present here by way of example. Nowadays, more and more terminals begin to support multi-bands CA characteristics, which makes CA terminals can fully use multi-band network resources, improving terminal throughput and other performance. Because of the different frequency bands are not related to coordination or antenna pattern, the CA terminal of the CA wireless environment is different. For example, some terminals are in the poor CA area (low quality CA area) in multiple frequency bands and RSRP, although giving multiple frequency bands resources, the overall throughput of current CA users is not very large.

Figure 3.6 AI RF Enabling CA Roof

CCO based RF optimization is a scenario oriented CA feature enabling algorithm, which improves the capacity upper bound of CA characteristic in the multi band region, and forms a good complement to the RRM characteristics and CA characteristics. From the formal point of view, can be divided into two independent and coordinated. The former is RF collected within a specific area of CA and non-CA user distribution, coverage and quality of each CA band. The calculated optimal band coverage performance state using AI algorithm, through independent RF power or inclination adjustment method, realize the optimization for capacity maximization of each CA band; the latter is not only covering RF independent optimization of each CA band, but also output some local area optimization mode set to RRM (which area is what band combination mode, RRM mode) from the optimization set out some suitable choice mode, flexible mode output compatible with other RRM properties of the optimal.

The future of CCO based intelligent RF will participate in the scene oriented RRM characteristics to constantly improve the theoretical upper bound of RRM characteristics.

3.3.7 Virtual Grid Enabled Network Performance Optimization

Compared to traditional geographic grid, Visual Grid does not need to divide the grid according to actual locations, instead, the system measurements (such as RSRP) of multiple cells are used to define the grid. History KPI statistics were stored in Visual Grid, and used for grid level radio performance optimization.

Fig 3.7. Virtual Raster Example

In the inter-frequency, inter-systems and multi-frequency network scenarios, change the granularity of the current cell-level algorithm to the grid level can improve the performance of many features such as CA, MLB, inter-frequency and inter-systems handover, CSFB, and SRVCC. For example, in CA scenario, it usually configure SCC in a blind way to reduce the GAP measure of inter-frequency, however the carrier or PCI selected may not be best, even fail to configure. As shown in Figure below, UE1 and UE2 will select Cell12 as SCC when using blind configure, but UE2 may fail. UE1 and UE2 will select Cell12 and Cell22 as SCC respectively when using Visual Grid method.

Figure 3.8 SCC Selections in CA

For big data driven method, the system measurements of multiple cells act as wireless fingerprints which is used to associate the statistics and measurements stored in the grid. After that, the model can be build and then use to predict wanted statistics and measurements given the inter-frequency measurements. By doing so, suitable policy and action can be selected to improve the performance of many radio features.

3.3.8 User Portraits Enabled User Experience Optimization

User portraits refer to classify users by given features based on real data. Through user classification by wireless

network features and data, the wireless network can be targeted on-demand to provide the appropriate services to improve the user experience and network utilization.

There are many dimensions that describe user features in the wireless network. Such as RSRP, RSRQ, CQI describe the characteristics of the wireless environment; such as terminal type, chip type, transmission capacity describe the characteristics of the user type; service type, buffer length, etc. describe the feature of user demands ; and Further analysis features, such as location, movement speed, trajectory and so on.

Figure 3.9 Wireless Network User Portraits

For different wireless applications, we can choose different multidimensional feature combinations to classify users. For example, you can sort the user transmission priorities by the service type and buffer length; assign the appropriate cell access and presence policy to the user through the service type and the movement speed; using location of the appropriate feature, moving speed, motion trajectory, business type to find appropriate user pairing, and so on.

3.4 Emerging Physical Layer Technology

3.4.1 Wireless Big Data Assisted Channel Modeling

With mobile communication system moving forward to 5G and future, technologies of physical layer, such as millimeter-wave, massive MIMO, bring evolution to new radio interface protocol of physical layer. Measurement and modeling of wireless channel are fundamental in design, evaluation and deployment of wireless communication systems. For instance, Wireless World Initiative New Radio (WINNER) performed numerous channel measurements in various scenarios applying channel sounder. Based on these measurements, WINNER channel model was proposed. Since 2000, many companies, research institutions, colleges and universities in China carried out a lot of channel measurements, theoretical modeling work and published numerous international standards. The main demands of channel test for 5G and future communication systems are: (1) various scenarios with characteristics, like high throughput, high movement speed, high capacity and complex spatial features;(2) coexistence of channels with various frequencies (millimeter-wave band such as 3.5GHz, 28 GHz, 37 GHz, 39 GHz, and 64-71 GHz); (3) Measurement devices for multi-channel, high-accuracy and wide bandwidth (4) huge volume of the collected channel data.

Primitive modeling work of wireless channel mainly focused on the derivation of the 2D channel model, which was not suitable for three-dimensional characteristics of the wireless channel and novel scenarios. Therefore,

systematic channel measurements and modeling are still necessary. On the other hand, the devices for channel measurement at early stage were serial devices, which were too limited to support the future scenarios, so the parallel devices for channel measurement were desiderated. However, the research and development of the parallel devices for channel measurement have several difficulties and challenges, such as accurate synchronization of multi-channel, multiple calibration, high-speed storage of the original data and interference elimination among multi-channel.

In recent years, due to the development trend of mobile communication system to multi-antenna, wide bandwidth, multi-scenario, data of channel measurement appears the three of 4V properties of “Big Data”, i.e., volume, variety, value and velocity. Applying methods in Big Data, the channel impulse response (CIR) could be processed without considering its physical meaning, the channel characteristics could be extracted and the channel could be modeled with the characteristics. For example, principal component analysis (PCA) could be applied to analyze the amplitude matrixes; the sub-channels could be clustered according to the correlation among the sub-channels, thus the phase structure of the channel data could be figured out. Finally, the channel could be modeled from the perspective of amplitude and phase. Besides, channel modeling could apply the machine learning algorithms to accurate and generalized prediction of the channel fading. For instance, [18,19] proposed a cluster-nuclei channel modeling method, adopting the development of computer graphics and computer vision. A three-layer construction including wave, cluster-nuclei and channel is formed; cluster-nuclei is the cluster which aggregated by numerous paths according to particular rules, and dominates the channel impulse response generation in various scenarios and configurations. This modeling method combines the advantages of stochastic model and deterministic model, and applies the variation rules along features (like the antenna numbers, frequency, mobility, etc.) extracted from the channel data. Therefore, this modeling method could support various scenarios in future wireless communication systems, such as high movement speed scenario and massive MIMO scenario.

In the future, the tasks in channel modeling research, like the prediction of channel fading and the influence which scenarios have on channel, etc., could be abstracted to regression, classification and clustering. We can apply powerful algorithms of machine learning and data mining which can solve these problems efficiently, in order to acquire accurate and fast methods for channel fading prediction and simulation.

3.4.2 Wireless Big Data Enabled Spectrum Map

The arrival of big data era provides a solid technical foundation for the research and development of cognitive radio. Through effective mining of the key information in big spectrum data, we can capture a new perspective of multidimensional spectrum information. The big data-enabled full spectrum signal map is an integrated database that includes information about the RF signal environment, relevant regulations, policies, physical locations of devices, available services, and relevant historical experience, etc. Big data-enabled full spectrum signal map has a wide range of applications, such as dynamic spectrum allocation and sharing, radio management and spectrum anomaly monitoring, electromagnetic spectrum warfare, to name just a few. In order to meet the demand of 5G and IoT on spectrum resource, the domestic and foreign research mainly focuses on three aspects: spectrum situation sensing, spectrum situation generation and spectrum situation application.

(1) Spectrum situation sensing for the big data-enabled full spectrum signal map

Spectrum situation sensing is the precondition of spectrum situation generation and spectrum situation application, which is mainly responsible for acquiring the current state of the spectrum space, including spectrum hole information, spectrum radiation power information, spectrum modulation mode, spectrum access protocol and so on. Spectrum situation sensing is the key to realize dynamic spectrum access. The spectrum sensing technology can collect spectrum occupancy data from the wireless environment that serves as the basis for the study of big data-enabled full spectrum signal map. On the other hand, according to the actual situation of the big data-enabled full spectrum signal map, the deployment of the spectrum sensors can be optimized, which can save the sensing resource and improve the efficiency in using the spectrum data.

The wide-area spectrum situation sensing mainly includes three issues: i) optimal deployment of spectrum sensing network, ii) compressed spectrum sensing and iii) aggregation and fusion of mass spectrum sensing data. Firstly, in order to minimize the deployment cost of the network, the deployment of the spectrum sensing network should be optimized. Secondly, compressed sensing technology is promising to decrease the cost and improve the robustness of spectrum sensing. Then, mass spectrum data are aggregated and fused in the data center by using efficient aggregation theory and approaches, provided that the transmission capacity and reliability are guaranteed and the delay of aggregation transmission is as small as possible. There are several types of spectrum sensing methods, such as energy detection, matched filter detection, cyclic-stationary detection and eigenvalue-based detection. The energy detection method is widely used in dynamic spectrum access because it is easy to implement.

(2) The spectrum situation generation for big data-enabled full spectrum signal map

The spectrum situation generation is based on spectrum sensing and further analyzes and predicts the comprehensive situation and developing trend of spectrum state. The specific issues include multi-dimensional spectrum situation completion, multi-view spectrum situation visualization, high-dimensional spectrum situation analysis, spectrum situation prediction and so on. The big data-enabled full spectrum signal map can collect the spectrum data regularly from the monitoring nodes in the network, and make decisions based on the spectrum situation map to achieve reliable data fusion. The current main-stream construction method can be divided into two categories: the methods based on spatial statistics and the methods based on signal propagation model with deterministic transmitters' locations. The methods based on spatial statistics are based on mining the correlation in spatial domain and using mathematical statistics to characterize the spectrum data of a given area. Using spatial statistics and spectrum data at a given location, we can estimate the missing data by the function of the known data. The methods based on the known location of the transmitters can be used to infer the performance of the transmitter, and then estimate the signal strength of each position by applying the signal propagation model. Compared with the methods based on spatial statistics, the methods based on the signal propagation model can greatly reduce the amount of spectrum data required.

After the completion of spectrum situation, the data can be presented in multiple views, which is generally divided into the following four steps: 1. The data is uniformly vectorized and normalized. 2. To reduce the dimension and perform the projection for the attributes besides the time dimension and the space dimension. 3. To

aggregate and disaggregate the spectrum data according to the time dimension, the spatial dimension and the frequency dimension. 4. To design different visual models for realizing the visualization of high dimension spectrum situation. Finally, we can analyze the current radio environment intuitively through the big data-enabled full spectrum signal map, and can predict the changing trend of complex multidimensional spectrum environment by analyzing historical data and evolution rules.

(3) The spectrum situation applications of big data-enabled full spectrum signal map

In order to breakout the fixed allocation in traditional spectrum management and to avoid the low utilization of licensed spectrum bands in multi-dimension, cognitive radio came into being. The big data-enabled full spectrum signal map is the starter of cognitive radio. In cognitive radio networks, dynamic spectrum allocation is realized by observing, analyzing and processing the spectrum situation, so as to improve the spectrum utilization and realize effective management of the spectrum access order, and enable the spectrum sharing between authorized users and unauthorized users or multiple authorized users. In addition, the big data-enabled full spectrum signal map can represent the mapping relation between the physical position and the signal strength directly, and establish the signal strength database corresponding to the known position of the transmitters. The storage information includes geographical environment information, propagation models, the location of transmitters and the busy or idle state of spectrum. Therefore, big data-enabled full spectrum signal map can also be applied to indoor and outdoor positioning.

In addition, with the rapid development of internet of things, electromagnetic spectrum environment becomes increasingly complex and the number of spectrum attackers or malicious users also increases over time. For example, illegal broadcasters, Pseudo based stations, radio cheating equipment, and other illegal equipment are endangering people's normal life. Using spectrum situation or map to monitor and locate the anomalies becomes an effective way to ensure the spectrum security and to enable a secure electromagnetic spectrum environment for various services.

3.4.3 Agile PHY Transmission Optimization

◇ User aggregation oriented PHY design

Big data analytics can improve the transmission performance by leveraging traffic correlation in aggregated users, channel properties, internal relation between transmission patterns and error performance, probability distribution of user access and etc. With abundant data resource and improvement of prediction techniques, the accuracy of prediction can be highly improved, which enable the accurate prediction on traffic, access and transmission of wireless users.

Traditional communication assumes that the user traffics are independent with no correlations among them. But current research works recognize that there exist bias and correlation, together with the property of user aggregation. By using data mining, users can be divided into different groups to fully utilize the wireless resources by effectively designed transmission scheme.

◇ Machine Learning based MIMO transmission optimization

In those large-scale MIMO equipped future wireless communication scenarios, the computation complexity of determining the optimal transmission using matrix calculations becomes infeasible. In particular, when combined with multi-carrier technologies such as OFDM, the optimal transmission mode cannot be obtained in closed-form. Applying machine learning on massive MIMO link adaptation can deeply exploit the inherent connection among channel characteristics, transmission mode and error performance. Based on data-driven machine learning methods, the mapping relation can be effectively learned by observing the channel data and the corresponding error performance so as to select the optimal transmission mode for each channel realization. It is of vital significance to apply the combination of deep learning and classification algorithms in machine learning on feature extraction of the channel state information so that it can improve the adaptive learning ability and universality of the MIMO link, further reducing the computational complexity.

✧ Beam Sweeping optimization based on user distribution

In conventional initial access procedure of 5G NR, as the information link has not been established between the base station and the user for information interaction, the beam sweeping can only be performed in sequential manner to transmit the synchronization signal as shown in Figure 3.9. There may be a large number of beam-pair between the base station and the user, resulting in larger initial access delay and lower initial access efficiency. Based on big data technology, the probability of user distribution can be predicted according to the information provided by users (e.g., historical data of users' access delay, success rate of access, and beam direction etc.), so that the beam pattern of the base station, including beam direction and sweeping order, can be optimized according to the predicted user distribution in order to ensure that users can be quickly accessed. Such optimization of initial access beam sweeping based on big data analysis is suitable for scenarios where the user group has certain characteristics. For example, when the predicted probability of user distribution is relatively large in a certain direction within a period of time, the beam sweeping ought to be prioritized or the number of scanning sweeping ought to be increased in this direction, thereby reducing the delay of initial access and increasing the success rate of it.

Figure 3.9 An example of beam sweeping

4 Wireless Big Data Enabled Network Architecture

4.1 Architecture

In the 5G era, the wireless core network adopts the control plane (CP) and the user plane (UP) separation and network function virtualization, which enables flexible deployment of network functions. The core network introduces the network data analysis (NWDA) to the 5G standard, which is used to collect massive data of each function of the core network, including user mobility data, service flow data, billing information, and Network entity status data. The NWDA can analyze the collected data, and improve the QoS of the user service through policy control function (PCF), in order to enhance the user's service experience. NWDA can also collect and store a large number of user service data, based on which the operators can provide the user portrait, precision marketing, and cross-border services, such that the value of big data can be fully explored.

The radio access network architecture includes a central unit (CU) and a distribution unit (DU) of the gNodeB (gNB) [20]. The radio access network exhibits the characteristics of hierarchical architecture and distributed deployment. The gNB-CU and gNB-DU can collect massive wireless network data, e.g. wireless channel data, wireless measurement reports, wireless access layer data, wireless traffic data and wireless network operation and maintenance data. Based on the collected big data of the radio access network, they can perform the channel model optimization, wireless resource scheduling optimization, agile PHY transmission optimization, and generating big data enabled full spectrum map. Among the above mentioned, for the physical layer channel optimization modeling and prediction-based radio resource management optimization can be characterized by short validity duration of the data source, which requires real-time data collection and strong real-time characteristics of the processing data at the network data resource. Moreover, prediction can be conducted according to the strong real-time characteristics of the processed data using machine learning technology, and parameter optimization can be performed in the corresponding network entity based on the predict results, in order to achieve automatic real-time and closed-loop network optimization.

If centralized big data analytics network architecture is directly introduced in the radio access network, it will face the following challenges:

(1) **Data Privacy Challenges:** Data collected from the radio access network may carry user privacy information and user privacy may be exposed.

(2) **High data Transmission cost:** RTT, TTI and other data generated by the radio access network, especially the DU site, is huge in number of data rate (> 1 Gbps). If all the unprocessed data is uploaded to the centralized big data analysis node, the data transmission from DU to centralized big data analysis node cost so expensive.

(3) **Difficult online Training / Prediction in Real Time:** The validity of data in radio access network is very short, and data backhauling delay will can't realize real-time (< 10 s) training / prediction of data in centralized data analysis nodes.

(4) **The data processing is too computationally expensive:** Each site of the radio access network generates a large amount of data and aggregates the data of all sites to a centralized data analysis node, which consumes too large amount of computing resources and becomes a bottleneck of the data analysis. In summary, the radio access

network big data analysis network architecture (RANDA) needs to be introduced to the wireless radio access network, which consists of various analysis modules including data acquisition, data storage, data processing, training models, model execution and parameter tuning optimization [21,22]. RANDA module includes the unit data analysis (CUDA) function for wireless network center and the distributed unit data analysis (DUDA) function for wireless network.

In order to meet the real-time requirements of the applications, the data analysis module must be deployed at the data source, to reduce the duration between the data processing, prediction / decision-making and network parameter optimization. Machine learning technology requires the use of existing big data training prediction / decision models to improve the accuracy and precision of prediction. However, in a wireless network, the independent gNB-DU devices typically suffer limited computational resources (even some gNBs may also be the same), such that the data analysis modules deployed on these devices can hardly support such high computational complexity tasks. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt the models to separate training from prediction method. For such separation, the parts with concentrated computational resources can undertake the tasks with large computational complexity including the model training, while independent gNB-DU and resource-constrained gNodeB can achieve the prediction tasks with the smaller computational complexity.

For the application of network optimization and planning, the data analysis module of the data source can store the radio access network data, which is uploaded to the network operation and maintenance entity for further processing. Such application requires the data service interface to BOSS and other network entities' data analysis function, accept the data subscription for BOSS and other network entity, in order to provide the appropriate data services.

Fig 4.1 The Architecture of Wireless Big Data Analytics

4.2 Big Data Module Function Definition

NWDA is a carrier-controlled network data analysis logic entity that can provide network data analysis results to PCF, which further performs the QoS policy decision based on the network data analysis results. NWDA also needs to provide the data subscription service for the BOSS and upload the preprocessed subscribed data to the BOSS / OSS, for further big data operations and services.

RANDA is primarily adopted to support data-driven intelligent radio resource management and physical layer or higher layer optimization in the RAN. The RANDA should interact both the control plane and user plane of the RAN to realize the data collection and policy configuration. It also needs to provide data subscription services for NWDA and BOSS / OSS, and upload pre-processed subscription data to NWDA and BOSS / OSS for further big data operations and services. RANDA can also subscribe to the NWDA data analysis results for the RAN-side service optimization. RANDA includes CUDA and DUDA.

CUDA is used in quasi real-time optimization for RRC, SDAP, PDCP and other protocol layers (such as, multi-connection, interference management, mobility management, etc.). More specifically, it includes the data analysis, the quasi real-time predicting, decision-making model training, the online model prediction, and the strategy generation and configuration based on the predict results, in order to provide DUDA data feature and model subscription distribution. CUDA can support both master and slave modes. The slave CUDA can request the master CUDA to perform some computational tasks, such as model training; while the master CUDA can conduct some computationally intensive model training for the slave CUDA, and offer some network-level collaborative optimization recommendations.

DUDA is adopted for the real-time RAN data collection and preprocessing, prediction, parameter optimization and training tasks with low computational complexity in DU (eg PHY \ MAC \ RLC). DUDA needs to offer data feature needed for training prediction / decision models after preprocessing to the CUDA, while CUDA can assist DUDA to conduct some computationally intensive model training tasks. Assisted by CUDA, the trained model can be sent to the DUDA for installation, perform real-time prediction / decision-making based on the real-time collected data, and generate the corresponding strategy based on the prediction results, in order to perform real-time close-loop control for the DU's process (such as scheduling, Link adaptation, etc.).

NWDA and RANDA (CUDA and DUDA) form a hierarchical and distributed deployment of data-driven intelligent network architecture, to improve the big-data service in the wireless network.

4.3 Interface

N23 interface connects NWDA and PCF, which transmits PCF and NWDA subscription information. PCF receive the network data analysis results through the N23 interface from the NWDA,, such as the congestion information of a specific Slice.

For RANDA, it is necessary to introduce the F1-D interface between CUDA and DUDA for data subscriptions / distributions between CUDA and DUDA, as well as the subscriptions and distributions of predictive / policy models. The interface definition between CUDA and CU-C and CU-U can provide more flexibility in supporting multi-scene deployments, and thus facilitates rapid iterative updates of network capabilities. N7 interface needs to be introduced between RANDA and NWDA to subscribe to and distribute processed data sets and data analysis results.

The interface and functionality between NWDA / RANDA and BOSS / OSS are subject to further study.

5 Wireless Big Data Platform Capabilities/Environment

5.1 Platform Requirements and Definitions

To support the fast-evolving data driven wireless services, the following five capabilities are required for the wireless big data platform: 1) big data clusters management capability; 2) big data analytics capability; 3) wireless networks, wireless transmissions and wireless applications support capability; 4) self-optimization, iterative update and continuous integration capability; 5) the AI/ML framework support capability.

The key features of wireless big data platform are summarized as follows:

- (1) **Simple and unified management interface:** The management interface is expected to effectively support the wireless big data platform construction, operation and maintenance services. It needs to support of forming a distributed wireless big data platform via the management interface. In addition, different big data software and an integrated big data capacity platform can be built according to the different hardware resources of components. For the user interface, a powerful engineering management capabilities and unified operating interface are desired
- (2) **Efficient off-line data analysis:** To efficiently deal with the mass amount of structured, semi-structured and unstructured data, the **wireless** big data platform needs to be able to do unify processing for different types of different systems. In addition, specific efforts are also needed for fast and stable processing of wireless big data.
- (3) **Real-time online data analysis:** For some wireless applications, the platform needs to provide real-time analysis capabilities to make timely decisions. The timescale for the real-time decision can be hourly, minute, second, or even millisecond.
- (4) **Support Offline algorithm:** Data analysis usually provides an elementary statistical analysis. For a deeper analysis, machine learning algorithm maybe needed to build a dedicated decision model. The wireless big data platform needs to provide the off-line algorithm for the original off-line data analysis, e.g., the model training. The offline algorithm mainly refers to non-incremental algorithms. Take the wireless network

optimization use cases for example, instead of building complex mathematical models through manual experience, the wireless big data platform helps to build a data driven model, which is expected to obtain a more accurately and practically mapping and provide automatically suggestions.

- (5) **Support Online algorithm:** Online data analysis provides real-time feedback for fast and timely respond and decision-making. The online algorithm mainly focuses on the incremental algorithm or the reinforcement algorithm that can make the previously constructed model evolve in real time. It helps to reduce the human intervention and avoid the knowledge of waste..

5.2 Framework of wireless big data platform

A wireless big data platform can be built based on the cloud or physical servers. The framework of the wireless big data platform is shown in Figure 4.1. The platform is divided into three layers, namely the data acquisition and pre-processing layer, the big data computing layer and the application/algorithm layer. It uses the corresponding interface between the different components for isolation.

Figure 4.1 Framework of wireless big data platform

For the data acquisition and preprocessing layer, we mainly consider the collection of the commercial network data, laboratory simulation data and third-party data. Data transmission includes both offline transmission and online transmission according to the application requirements. As the data form is very diverse, a unified representation is desired. Moreover, we need to preprocess the data by cleaning, feature extraction before using the

data for specific applications. With regard to specific use cases, the data can be stored in a big data database or directly input to the algorithms.

The big data computing system platform layer is composed of the big data analytic part and management part. The management part is mainly responsible for big data platform operation and maintenance, platform capacity expansion, etc. As for the big data analytics part, we need to take account of the wireless services' requirements on the platform and capability of the different physical servers. For example, a machine that computes superior performance can deploy Spark services to support online and off-line computing. While machines with sufficient storage space and better performance, Spark and HDFS services can be deployed to support off-line processing of massive amounts of data. As communication between servers often limits the real-time capabilities of cluster computing in big data clusters, it is recommended to use fiber, optical switching and other more rapid communication media, to speed up the communication between the nodes.

For the application layer/algorithm platform, the following three aspects should be considered. The first is the project management capabilities. It is required to be friendly to users with different backgrounds. The second is the algorithm. Many outstanding machine learning library can be integrated. The machine learning algorithm can be divided into classical machine learning algorithms, incremental learning algorithms, deep learning and reinforcement learning. For classical machine learning algorithm, the needs of stand-alone and distributed clusters needs to be taken into account, blending in such as scikit-learn, H2O.ai, Spark MLlib and so on. Incremental learning can refer to the StreamDM system developed by Huawei Noah Labs. For deep learning algorithms, the platform can be integrated with Tensorflow, Caffe, Theano and other deep learning system. For the Reinforcement learning algorithms, Caffe2, DeeR, Tensorflow and other existing system framework can be considered. The third is the efficient communication to support real-time online analysis and algorithm construction for wireless service.

5.3 Data representation in wireless big data platform

The data processing performance of the platform heavily relies on the data representation. It is not only affect the storage of data, but also affect the efficiency of data processing. Here, we provide some guidance for the data representation of different data structures.

In general, data can be divided into structured data, semi-structured data and unstructured data. Two-dimensional table is usually used to express the structured data. Call history record, words, KPI data from the commercial network or laboratory simulation can be regarded as structured data. Unstructured data is not convenient to be presented as two-dimensional logic table. It generally includes all formats of office documents, text, pictures, images and audio/video and so on. Compared with structured data, unstructured data usually has unknown data semantic information and requires large space for single record storage. Therefore, it is difficult to store and retrieval the unstructured data. Semi-structured data is between fully structured and completely unstructured data, such as HTML documents. It is generally self-describing, the structure and content are mixed together.

For unstructured data, it is recommended to use a table containing the metadata of three fields to represent: number, description (varchar (1024)), content index (blob). Metadata uses structured data representation to manage

the source data. Through the content description, we can know the meaning of the data. Through the content index, we can obtain the corresponding raw data.

For the storage and representation of semi-structured data, two widely used methods are suggested:

- (1) Decomposed the semi-structured data into structured data by extracting the the required fields. If the data does not contain certain attribute, the vacancy or default value can be used. The rest of the data can be integrated added to the memo field as the note information. This method is convenient for querying. But it lacks flexibility of expansion, which is unable to handle the extra information beyond the premilitary design.
- (2) Use XML format to organize the unstructured data and save to the CLOB field. Information of different categories can be stored in different nodes of XML. The advantages of this approach are: it is easy to expand the information by simply changing the corresponding DTD or XSD. Disadvantages are the relatively low query efficiency.

6 Impact on the Standardization

6.1 Standards progress in 3GPP SA2

In the 3GPP SA2#121 meeting, May 2017, the Big Data/AI based Standard project named FS_eNA (Study of enablers for Network Automation for 5G) was approved with the support of 24 companies. The project was planned to be discussed in Q1 2018 at the 3GPP standard meeting.

Figure 7.1 5G architecture with the NWDAF

The work will study the necessary data to expose to NWDAF and the necessary NWDAF outputs in order to at least support (non-exhaustive list):

- Customized mobility management per UE e.g. paging enhancements and mobility pattern

- 5G QoS enhancement e.g. 5G QoS target fulfilment verification and QoS profile for non-standardized 5QI
- Dynamic traffic steering and splitting, UPF selection, UE traffic routing policies based on UE's service usage behaviour
- Service classification based resource management e.g. background data transfer for MNO and 3rd party service provider and TV content

No algorithms or NWDA internal behavior is to be specified, which is out of the scope of 3GPP and the SID will focus on how to collect data and how to feedback network data analytics to the network.

6.2 Potential Impact on 3GPP RAN3

As discussion in chapter 4, a hierarchical, distributed network architecture is desired to enable the wireless big data assisted network design, optimization and physical layer enhancement. Besides NWDA, RAN data analytics also need to be introduced at the RAN side. The potential standardization impact on 3GPP RAN3 is listed as follows:

1. Analyzing the classic application scenarios and use case, which supported by RANDA;
2. Defining the functionality of RANDA (CUDA+DUDA);
3. Defining the interface and procedure of the RANDA (CUDA+DUDA).

With the deepening of the research, a study item maybe promote in 3GPP RAN3 work group for standardization.

7 Summary

This is the era of big data and artificial intelligence, which has been extensively recognized as two of the most momentous driving forces for productivity promoting and efficiency improvements, leading to remarkable innovation and commercial success. Driven by the increasing demands of mobile internet and the internet of things, the wireless networks are expected to provide diversified services for distinguished scenarios and correspondingly makes the network much more complex. Meanwhile, explosive data are generated from wireless networks. These highly dimensional, heterogeneous, complex, unstructured and unpredictable data creates great opportunities. With the powerful artificial intelligence algorithms, the wireless big data will definitely bring profound impacts on the design, optimization, operation and maintenance of the wireless network. The wireless big data and AI are envisioned to be the next disruptive elements for 5G and beyond, which is expected to significantly enhance the network performance and user experiences along with much reduced costs.

This whitepaper introduces the definition, source, category and the key characteristics of the wireless big data. Classical big data processing method are briefly reviewed, focusing on its applications on wireless network related areas. The typical scenarios and use cases of wireless big data are studied along with the key enabling technologies. The potential impacts of wireless big data on the design of network architecture, protocol stack, signaling procedure, and physical layer technologies is also investigated in the use cases. Driven by the use cases, we strive to come up with a conceptual reference architecture design for the data driven intelligent wireless network. The

wireless big data platform capabilities/environment is further discussed. Last but not the least, the preliminary views on challenges and impact on the standardization are presented.

As the key guiding document for future works, this whitepaper is expected to help readers better understand the wireless big data and AI studies for the smart 5G network. Continual efforts on this research topic will be carried out to tackle the challenges. A collective wisdom and especially more efforts among SIG members and others parterres are expected. The Latest achievements will be presented in annual updates of this white paper or technology review reports.

We sincerely invite all mobile operators, telecom equipment manufacturers and traditional IT system manufacturers, as well as industrial and academic research institutions of interest to contribute to the research on the big data driven intelligent mobile network and work together to deliver the smart 5G vision.

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Glossary

3GPP	the 3rd Generation Partner Project
5G	the Fifth-Generation mobile communications
BOSS	Business & Operation Support System
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
CCO	Coverage and Capacity Optimization
CRDA	Coordinated RAN Data Analytics

CUDA	Central-Unit Data Analytics
CU	Central Unit
CSFB	Circuit Switched Fallback
D2D	Device to Device
DPI	Deep Packet Inspection
DU	Distributed Unit
DUDA	Distributed-Unit Data Analytics
GPS	Global Positioning System
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identification Number
IMEI	International Mobile Equipment Identity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KQI	Key Quality Indicator
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCES	Multi-RAT Cooperation Energy-Saving System
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output
MPP	Massive Parallel Processing
NWDA	Network Data Analytics
OPEX	Operation Expense
OSS	Operation Support System
OTT	Over-The-Top
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCI	Physical Cell Identity
PCF	Policy Control Function
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RANDA	RAN Data Analytics
RLC	Radio Link Control
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSRP	Reference Signal Receiving Power
RSRQ	Reference Signal Receiving Quality

SCC	Secondary Component Carrier
SDAP	Service and Data Adaptation Protocol
SRVCC	Single Radio Voice Call Continuity
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
TA	Tracking Area
VoD	Video on Demand
WINNER	Wireless World Initiative New Radio

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